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Abstract: *Political newspaper discourse has an inter-discursive vector of development, in it we see a combination of political discourse, media discourse and newspaper discourse (for example, publicity, influencing function, etc.). Since political newspaper discourse requires a response from the readership (understanding, agreement with the presented assessment) we should also talk about discourse as a social interaction. To engage in interaction means to engage in a continuous process of "negotiations" related both to assumptions about what others intend to report and to the control of their own speech production. For political newspaper discourse, the status of the speaker is important, that is, the figure of a political figure, the status of a political party, the ideological format of a newspaper publication.*

Keywords: *newspaper, political, discourse, text, information, communication, media.*

The dominant feature of political discourse is political communication, that is, "speech activity focused on the promotion of certain ideas, emotional impact on the citizens of the country and encouraging them to take political action, to develop public consent, adoption and justification of socio-political decisions in conditions of a plurality of points of view in society". At the same time, political linguistics is interested not only in the transmission of information, but also "everything related to the perception and assessment of political reality in the process of communicative activity".

As part of the analysis of political discourse, such aspects of political communication as genres of political speech, communicative portraits of individual political figures, tactics, techniques and strategies in speech, as well as its figurative and expressive means are studied. It is noteworthy that when studying all these features, a discursive approach is used, that is, "each specific text is considered in the context of the political situation in which it was created, in its relation to other texts, taking into account the objectives, political views and personal qualities of the author, the specifics of the perception of this text by various people. It is necessary to take into account the role that this text can play in the system of political texts and, more broadly, in the political life of the country. For example, the same idea and even the same statements will be perceived completely differently in the text of a newspaper article by a journalist and in an official statement by the President of the Russian Federation or the President of the United States of America". The choice of the

storylines of the presented problem, the gradual appearance of the participants of the events in the text version, the presentation of the author's attitude to the presented information – all this and much more affects the understanding of the speech message by the addressee.

Thus, political discourse is a discourse of power, since there is a struggle for power- in the political arena, for fundamental group values, and the political newspaper discourse we are considering in this paper is a kind of political discourse. E.A. Bocharova defines political newspaper discourse as "a speech genre that is a complex communicative event and at the same time a verbal formalization of this a communicative event, and has a certain role composition of participants".

As a rule, the main participants of political newspaper discourse are considered to be a journalist (the addressee of this discourse), as well as a potential readership (the addressee of this discourse). It is important to emphasize here that political newspaper discourse is characterized by publicity and often by formality. The topics of political newspaper discourse are quite wide: from issues of public administration in one's own country to the presentation of political events in different countries. The main purpose of political newspaper discourse is the informational function, which consists in transmitting the necessary information about the political situation in the country and the world. This information must meet the following conditions: be truthful and reliable, clear and easy to remember, accurate in presentation. The purpose of the next function – persuasive – is to ensure that the text that is created by the communicator is weighty and indisputable. To achieve this goal, it must be logical, touch the sphere of feelings, and also have personal and objective meanings. The text should be convincing, grounded and stored in memory. The third main function of political newspaper discourse is motivation. It is not enough just to give information, it is also required that this information prompts to accept the assessment of the presented that the communicator gives. It follows from this that the main purpose of the text is to interest the readership by providing it with the most accurate, complete and reasonable data that can reason with it and agitate for active action in the final result.

Political newspaper discourse has an inter-discursive vector of development, in it we see a combination of political discourse, media discourse and newspaper discourse (for example, publicity, influencing function, etc.). Since political newspaper discourse requires a response from the readership (understanding, agreement with the presented assessment) we should also talk about discourse as a social interaction. To engage in interaction means to engage in a continuous process of "negotiations" related both to assumptions about what others intend to report and to the control of their own speech production. For political newspaper discourse, the status of the speaker is important, that is, the figure of a political figure, the status of a political party, the ideological format of a newspaper publication.

The designated discourse expresses the whole complex of relations between a person and society, which means that it has a direct impact on the education or change in the recipient's worldview. Like most texts of a political orientation, political newspaper discourse contains extra linguistic information (a picture of the world) and symbolic information (a picture of the world of an ideologically oriented representative of a newspaper publication transmitted using a linguistic sign). So, by political newspaper discourse we mean a kind of political discourse that is aimed at a mass addressee and is characterized by a persistent intention of the addressee, an expanded theme, emotionality.

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